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SIMULATION OF THE PROGRESSIVE FAILURE OF CFRP AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURE

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Temperature Dependency of CFRP

- Composite structures are (unavoidably) subjected to various (elevated) temperatures during service
- Epoxy matrix material properties decline with temperature

- UD CFRP with increasing temperature
 - E_1, X_T →
 - E_2, G_{12} ↓
 - X_C, Y_T, Y_C, S_L ↓
 - G_{IC} → / ↗
 - G_{IIC} →

[Airbus]

[Polestar]

The matrix's mechanical performance decreases with increasing environmental temperature and negatively influences the damage tolerance.

Temperature Dependency of Damage Tolerance: Approach

Determination of Impact Resistance and Residual Strength

UD-Prepreg: Hexcel HexPly M21/T800s 265 g/m²
T_g: 171 °C (Onset)

Layup: [45/0/-45/90]_{2s}
Laminate Thickness: 4.1 mm

LVI

CAI

ASTM D7136 M
Impact Parameters:
Energy: 15-21 J
Temperature: 20 °C – 80 °C

ASTM D7137 M
Temperature: 20 °C + 80 °C

Simulation of LVI and CAI at Elevated Temperature

- Mechanical characterisation of M21/T800s at temperatures between 20 °C and 100 °C
- Implementation of temperature dependency into the Continuum Damage code CompDam
- Simulation of LVI and CAI under temperature influence with Abaqus/Explicit

Temperature Dependency of Damage Tolerance: Approach Simulation

Material Characterisation

Interpolation Functions

Implementation into CDM and Single Element Testing

CDM is based on CompDam

LVI and CAI Simulation

Abaqus/Explicit

Temperature Dependency of Damage Tolerance: Material Characterisation

Stress-free temperature: 171 °C (determined with a bistable laminate)

Mechanical Properties

Temperatures: 20 °C - 100 °C

Tensile Tests: E_1 , X_T , $E_2(T)$, $Y_T(T)$.

ASTM D 3039

Compression Tests: $Y_C(T)$, $X_C(T)$,

ASTM D 6641

Shear Tests: $G_{12}(T)$, $S_L(T)$

ASTM D 3518

Interlaminar Properties:

Temperature: 20 °C

Mode I: G_{IC}

ASTM D 5528

Mode II: G_{IIC}

ASTM D 7905

Material Model: Failure

Fibre Failure:

Tension (Temperature independent):

Damage initiation: Max-stress criterion

Damage propagation: Bi-linear energy based degradation

Compression:

Damage initiation: Temperature dependent max-stress criterion

Damage propagation: Temperature independent

Bi-linear energy based degradation

Matrix Failure:

Damage initiation:

- Temperature dependent
- Accounts for friction on fracture plane

Damage Propagation:

- Temperature independent Benzeggagh-Kenane Law

CDM is based on CompDam

Single-Element Tests: Temperature-Dependent Failure Envelope

$\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22}$ Plane

$\sigma_{22} - \tau_{12}$ Plane

Material Model: Shear Nonlinearity

Non-linear shear behaviour is represented by the Ramberg-Osgood equation:

$$\gamma_{12} = \frac{\tau_{12} + \alpha_{PL}(T) \text{sign}(\tau_{12}) |\tau_{12}|^{n_{PL}(T)}}{G_{12}(T)}$$

Shear Modulus

Ramberg-Osgood Parameter

Shear Response

Abaqus Cohesive Contact

Quadratic Stress Initiation Criterion:

$$\left(\frac{\langle t_n \rangle}{t_n^0(T)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_1}{t_1^0(T)}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_t}{t_t^0(T)}\right)^2 \geq 1$$

Qualitative interface strength degradation is coupled to experimental values:

Mode I initiation to Y_T

Mode II initiation to S_T

Degradation:

Temperature independent Benzeggagh-Kenane Law

Low Velocity Impact: Top Layer Damage

With increasing temperature failure modes change:
Severe fibre failure occurs.

LVI: Delamination Damage

At different temperatures, different impact energies can result in the same delamination area.

CAI: Residual Strength

Delamination

Temperature has a more decisive influence on the compressive residual strength than the impact parameters.

Understanding and adapting the matrix's damage behaviour is fundamental to improve the damage tolerance of high-performance composites.

The addition of carbon nanoparticles into the matrix introduces additional energy-consuming damage mechanisms and increases the damage tolerance.

The composite's layup can control the occurring matrix damage modes. Thin-ply, bio-inspired helicoidal layups enable delamination-free composites.

The matrix's mechanical performance decreases with increasing environmental temperature and negatively influences the damage tolerance.

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